

RUSSIAN LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODOLOGY AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH OTHER SUBJECTS

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ANNOTATSIYA	KALIT SO‘ZLAR
<p>Hozirgi vaqtda metodologiya maxsus mustaqil fan hisoblanadi. Shunga asoslanib, xorijiy mamlakatlarning yetakchi olimlari chet tilini o‘qitish metodikasi, uning kategoriyalari, qonunlari, atamalari, vazifalari haqida aniq tushunchalarni shakllantiradilar. Rus tilini chet tili sifatida o‘qitish metodikasi mustaqil o‘quv intizomiga aylandi.</p>	<p><i>chet tilini o‘qitish metodikasi, uning kategoriyalari, qonunlari, didaktika va psixologiya.</i></p>
АННОТАЦИЯ	КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА
<p>В настоящее время методология представляет собой особую науку, самостоятельную науку. На основе этого у ведущих ученых советских и зарубежных стран сформировались четкие представления о методике преподавания иностранного языка, его категориях, законах, терминах и задачах. Методика преподавания русского языка как иностранного стала самостоятельной учебной дисциплиной.</p>	<p>методика преподавания иностранного языка, ее категории, закономерности, дидактика и психология.</p>
ABSTRACT	KEY WORDS
<p>Currently, methodology is a special science, an independent science. Based on this, the leading scientists of the Soviet and foreign countries formed clear concepts about the methodology of teaching a foreign language, its categories, laws, terms, and tasks. The methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language has become an independent educational discipline.</p>	<p><i>foreign language teaching methodology, its categories, laws, didactics and psychology.</i></p>

The method of teaching the Russian language to foreigners, like other methods, is based on the conclusions and generalizations of some disciplines, primarily linguistics, didactics and psychology. The findings of linguistics,

psychology and didactics form the scientific basis of the methodology of teaching the Russian language to foreigners.

Teaching methods depend on different educational goals and conditions, on non-linguistic factors. The subject of the methodology is the teaching of the Russian language as a means of communication - it defines the ultimate goal - "mastery of the language". Teaching Russian as a foreign language (and any subject in general) is a joint activity of the teacher and students. In order for students to master the language, the teacher must perform certain educational (teaching) actions: explain new material, assign tasks, ask questions and check the correctness of the answer, etc. Students should also be active and perform several actions during the learning process: reading the text, learning words, doing exercises, answering the teacher's questions, etc.

In traditional forms of education (face-to-face), the actions of students are always determined and controlled by the teacher. It is he who decides what students should do, at what point, in what sequence, and for what purpose. And, of course, he determines for himself what and how to do in the classroom (even outside the classroom). It directly teaches and teaches students how to learn. But any teacher knows that the teacher's teaching efforts do not always give the desired result. It is necessary to explain to him what methods to use, how to combine them with each other, how to behave in the audience to achieve the desired goal. In other words, we must teach him to consciously manage the learning process, including consciously organizing his learning activities, so that the learning process gives us good results¹.

The topic of the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language is the educational process management system. A system aimed at the most effective mastering of the Russian language by students. Teaching Russian is understood as learning to speak, communicate and express opinions in Russian, even in the absence of a language environment. Thus, the methodology has its research subject, which is not repeated in any discipline - teaching another language as a means of communication. This category defines the content of the entire educational process, the types of speech activities that must be mastered, and the levels of language knowledge that must be achieved in each of these types.

The main subject for methodology is linguistics. Teaching practice shows that not all methods of describing the Russian language are equally effective in teaching foreigners. It is also impossible to make teaching effective without the participation of linguistics. Pedagogical factors should also be taken into account in the educational process. Among them, there are such phenomena and laws studied by general pedagogy. For example, the relationship between education and upbringing.

This is especially important when teaching the Russian language in a country where representatives of more than 120 nationalities live. Didactics is a branch of pedagogy that defines general teaching methods. Teaching is a joint activity of the teacher and students. Now we need to clarify what has been said: learning is a joint active cognitive activity organized, encouraged and controlled by the teacher. Let's understand this definition and at the same time formulate the most important didactic principles.

1. What is a "joint" activity? As mentioned above, the teacher and students strive for one common goal. To achieve this, both the teacher and the students must perform certain actions. And the teacher must ensure that the students do everything in the right order and with the right effect. Therefore, one of the main didactic principles is the principle of collectivity.

2. The second is the principle of operation. For teaching to be effective, students must show initiative, have an independent and creative approach to the subject, and be able to work independently in class and outside of class. Ensuring and organizing students' activity is the most important task of the teacher.

3. Didactics suggests how to provide this activity. Students need to be presented with a problem, to solve which they need the knowledge, skills and competencies included in the curriculum. All learning must turn into solving a series of increasingly complex problems. This is required by the didactic principle of problematization. When we teach Russian to foreigners, first of all communicative problems arise here: how to communicate in a certain situation, on a certain topic. If the student feels the need to solve such a problem, he will easily use the words and grammatical structures introduced in the lesson.

4. What does "feel the need" mean? So, the problem presented to the student alone does not ensure his activity. There must be a need to solve this problem. Appropriate motivation must be created. The motivational function of the teacher is the most important. The principle of motivation or the principle of motivation is a special didactic principle. A person learns a foreign language not only to use it for communication. Students' activity in the psychological acquisition of the language is a typical cognitive activity: as a result, students enrich themselves - mind, personality, activity.

5. One of the important didactic principles is the principle of developmental education. In teaching a foreign language, it means that we have to present students with increasingly complex communicative and cognitive tasks in a certain sequence. It should be noted that not every problem is didactically valuable and arouses a motivational attitude in the student².

All the above principles of any teaching should be implemented in the methodology of a specific subject, in our case, in the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language. All these principles are interrelated and offer us a unique model of the educational process.

Communication is an activity. Activities can be not only communicative: there are work activities, cognitive educational activities and game activities. But it always has a fundamentally unified psychological structure, that is, the laws of its formation are also the same. It follows that both communication and training for such communication should be subject to general psychological laws.

When a person starts any activity, he has a conscious goal, he knows what he wants to achieve, a motive - that is, there is a need to achieve this goal. For example, you want to master the Russian language - this is the goal. And here the motives can be very different: business, socio-cultural (interest in Russian literature, Russian history, etc.), educational (reading literature in Russian as a specialty), etc. Activity begins with the emergence of a goal and the desire to achieve it (motive) and ends when this motive is satisfied, and the goal is achieved.

Orientation is important in communication. When a teacher first comes into the classroom, he or she must gather as much information as possible about the students. After orientation, the second stage of activity begins - planning, then implementation of the plan - actual action. And finally, the last step is to control the effectiveness of the activity.

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